

CONTEXTUALIZED e-GAME-BASED VOCABULARY ENHANCEMENT ACTIVITIES FOR GRADE 8 LEARNERS

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Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop and evaluate contextualized e-Game-based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners at San Jose National High School, Division of Antipolo City during the School Year 2023-2024. The descriptive method of research using an adapted survey questionnaire as the main research instrument was employed in this paper. Fifteen (15) English teachers and fifteen (15) English experts were asked to assess the developed vocabulary enhancement material in terms of Content Quality, Instructional quality, and Technical Quality. It was found out that the English teachers and expert-respondents evaluated the developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners in terms of content quality, instructional quality, and technical quality with grand weighted mean ratings of 3.80 and 3.68 respectively, verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree (SA) and indicated no significant difference on their evaluations. The two groups of respondents gave comments and suggestions for further improvement of the developed learning material.

Keywords: *enhancement activities, vocabulary, Grade 8*

Introduction

English is the primary instrument in communication (oral and written), and the exchange of meaning is at the heart of it. Language becomes an ultimate part of our lives as we engage in the production and reception of meanings. In purposive situations, every individual does not only look at language as a mere method with different components and rules that are expected to be known and mastered. It becomes more significant as language acts for every user as a tool with its essential contents, meanings and implications that can affect either the success or failure of sending and receiving messages.

In this connection, vocabulary is one of the most important components of English. To communicate well, one should have enough vocabulary and know how to use them correctly. It is one of the skills that should be mastered well as it links the five macro skills in reading, namely: viewing, listening, speaking, reading, and writing. According to Mukoroli (2021), word meaning is only one aspect of vocabulary; another is the way a language's vocabulary is organized, including how people use and remember words, how they learn new words, and the connections between words, phrases, and word categories.

In this sense, vocabulary involves more than just knowing a word's precise meaning; it also involves determining a word's appropriate usage in phrases or during communication, as well as how the word is employed in different contexts.

However, vocabulary is often taken for granted. Ulum (2018) stated that in EFL context, vocabulary is clearly one of the weakest and underestimated skills. Talavera (2018), on the other hand, expressed that vocabulary is the most neglected area in teaching English as a communicative process.

Relatively, incidental vocabulary learning through reading has its own limitations and prerequisites. Students' prior vocabulary knowledge, motivation, and independent learner strategy are some of the factors that determine its effectiveness.

As a matter of fact, students in the Philippines continue to be among the world's lowest in math, reading, and science, according to new PISA findings, with current test scores showing no substantial improvement over the country's performance in 2018.

The Philippines' poor score in the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) suggests that pupils in the country are five to six years behind in learning competencies, according to the Department of Education (Servallaos, 2023).

On a similar note, based on the result of posttest administered as part of the Phil-IRI at San Jose National High School, ninety-two (92) Grade 8 learners were still categorized as frustration readers who need enhancement activities to address their problems as regards reading, particularly their vocabulary skill. More so, these learners were also identified as students who lagged behind based on the result of their first quarter examination as reported in the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) and Least Mastered Skills (LMS).

Student success and learning depend heavily on engagement and motivation. Students that are engaged learn more, retain more, and enjoy learning activities more than their non-involved peers. Gamification is a new educational method that aims to boost student enthusiasm and engagement (Dichev & Dicheva, 2017).

Most research demonstrated that gamification of education is an important factor in student motivation and engagement. Gamification was also found to be useful in raising motivation (Rose, 2019).

Because of this, the researcher felt that students need to develop their vocabulary skills to improve their comprehension. The researcher also firmly believes that the developed enhancement activities would be of great help in enhancing the vocabulary skill of the Grade 8 students and their academic performance.

Research Questions

This research sought to develop and evaluate Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners at San Jose National High School, Division of Antipolo City during the school year 2023-2024. It addressed the following research problems specifically:

1. What are the top ten (10) least mastered vocabulary skills that could be developed into Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities based on the Phil-IRI result during the school year 2022-2023?
2. What are evaluations of the expert-respondents and teacher-respondents on the developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners in terms of the criteria listed below?
 - 2.1. Content Quality
 - 2.2. Instructional Quality
 - 2.3. Technical Quality
3. Is there a significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners with respect to the aforementioned criteria?
4. What are the comments/suggestions given by the respondents relative to the improvement of the developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners?

Literature Review

According to Ramos (2019), vocabulary serves as the foundation for second language (L2) acquisition. As a result, its relevance is intrinsically linked to the early phases of language acquisition. In addition, vocabulary acquisition is an ongoing process. It is the ongoing process of encountering new words in relevant and understandable settings.

Furthermore, Lessard (2019) noted that vocabulary knowledge is widely recognized as an important component of English language instruction. Students that lack vocabulary will struggle to communicate with and comprehend others. Similarly, the author stated that expanding one's language means empowering oneself. All the words in a human mind waiting to be employed in conversation contribute to the development of self-confidence.

Relatively, Krashen, as cited by Zainuddin (2019), mentioned that the learner needs to be exposed to a large amount of comprehensible input in their new language to acquire the language. This means that teachers should ensure that reading takes place not only within the classroom but also outside the four corners of the room. This is possible through supplementary activities.

In this regard, Olawale (2020) contended that the importance of creating improvement and intervention materials in the teaching-learning process should not be overlooked. It is critical to the successful interplay between teaching and learning. If properly produced, these resources will be beneficial and effective in terms of improving, facilitating, and making teaching and learning more fluid, vibrant, and tangible.

Escueta, et. al. (2020) discovered that technology-enabled behavioral therapies are two areas that hold significant promise. Computer-Aided Learning offers the ability to promote cognitive skill creation by reducing traditional instructor and classroom limits, enhancing investment efficiency. CAL, especially when combined with a customization option, has been proved to be highly helpful in assisting pupils, particularly with reading.

In comparison, gamification of education is a tactic for improving engagement that incorporates gaming elements into an educational environment. The idea is to achieve levels of involvement comparable to what games can typically produce. Gamification's key goals are to improve specific talents, offer objectives that give learning meaning, engage students, optimize learning, assist behavior change, and socialize (Krause et al. 2019).

Similarly, Ramirez and Squire (2019) proposed that gamification in education can provide students with more control over their learning and even provide feedback on their activities in respect to the structure and aims of their studies. It encourages people to rely on their own motivation by making daily tasks enjoyable and engaging.

Realo, et. al. (2022) attempted to increase Grade 8 pupils' vocabulary skills through localized game-based exercises. Consequently, the students' pre- and post-test results differ significantly. This study found that game-based activities, whether localized, digital, or conceived, significantly improved children's vocabulary skills.

Similarly, the study of Domingo (2023) aimed to provide and assess research-based supplemental learning materials for English 10 students. It was concluded that the developed Supplementary Learning Materials in Research for English 10 learners may be utilized as effective learning materials in teaching lessons in Research for English 10 learners.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive survey of research utilizing a survey questionnaire from DepEd that aids DepEd Regions, Divisions

and Schools in selecting and obtaining excellent digital and non-digital resources in response to identified local educational requirements.

According to Skinner (2020) the descriptive survey method is designed to gather information about the present/existing conditions. It also refers to detailed explanations of the variables that result in the patterns of change and stability that have been outlined. These are entirely dissimilar from descriptions in and of themselves.

Respondents

The sources of data in this study as shown in Table 1, are the 15 experts and 15 English teachers who served as respondents of the developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners.

Instrument

The researcher utilized the DepEd LRMDs evaluation tool in order to have a high level of confidence that the indicators supplied in the instrument accurately reflect the research topic and are comprehensive and answerable. The tool which was modified was composed of two parts. The first part consisted of statements on the evaluation of the developed e-game-based vocabulary enhancement activities with respect to content quality, instructional quality, and technical quality. The second part reflected the comments and suggestions of the respondents to further improve the developed learning material.

Procedure

The ten Least Mastered Skills of Grade 8 Learners from the PHILIRI result SY 2022-2023 were identified. Then the survey questionnaire was adapted and modified from DepEd Guidelines and Processes for Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) Assessment and Evaluation. It was then endorsed to validators for the revalidation of its modification. The revalidated survey questionnaire was used in evaluation of the e-game-based enhancement activities. The developed material was evaluated based on the following criteria a) content quality, (b) instructional quality, and (c) technical quality.

Then, the researcher prepared the necessary communication letters noted by the adviser containing the request to conduct the study. It was sent to the Division of Antipolo, Schools Division Superintendent, for approval which was used as an attachment to the letter of request to the school principals of the selected public schools in the Division for the researcher to administer the survey instrument.

With approval, the researcher sent the survey in print form to the chair of the English Department, who then gave it to the English language experts and the English 8 instructors so they could evaluate the e-game-based vocabulary-building exercises that had been developed. The material was sent via the respondents' email addresses.

The researcher was concerned about the confidentiality of the respondent's online privacy; thus, the anonymity of the teacher respondents was ensured by the researcher.

The data gathered was consolidated with the guidance and advice of the statistician and adviser. As advised by the statistician, the researcher kept the printed copy of the survey for the confidentiality of the teacher's responses.

Results and Discussion

Top Ten (10) Least Mastered Vocabulary Skills that could be Developed into Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities Based on the Phil-IRI Result During the School Year 2022-2023

Table 1. *Top Ten (10) Least Mastered Vocabulary Skills that could be Developed into Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities*

<i>Least Mastered Vocabulary Skills</i>	<i>Responses</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Determining the meaning of words and expressions through Inference or General Text Clue	1015	50.000	1
Arriving at meanings through Cause-and-Effect or Reason-Result Clue	1368	33.333	2
Determining the meaning of words and expressions that reflect the local culture by noting context clues	1208	33.333	3
Determining the type of context clue used in a statement	1147	33.333	4
Analyzing intentions of words or expressions used in propaganda techniques	1815	25.000	5
Using Comparison or Sameness Clue in figuring out the meaning of difficult words	1600	20.000	6
Determining the meaning of words and expressions through Explanation or Example Clue	2091	20.000	7
Using Antonym or Contrast Clue in unlocking the meaning of unfamiliar words	1268	20.000	8
Determining the meaning of words and expressions through Definition or Statement Clue	2531	16.667	9
Determining the meaning of words and expressions through Synonym or Restatement Clue	3504	12.500	10

The top ten least mastered vocabulary skills according to rank are: Rank 1: Determining the meaning of words and expressions through Inference or General Text Clue; Rank 2: Arriving at meanings through Cause-and-Effect or Reason-Result Clue; Rank 3: Determining the meaning of words and expressions that reflect the local culture by noting context clues; Rank 4: Determining the type of context

clue used in a statement; Rank 5: Analyzing intentions of words or expressions used in propaganda techniques; Rank 6: Using Comparison or Sameness Clue in figuring out the meaning of difficult words; Rank 7: Determining the meaning of words and expressions through Explanation or Example Clue; Rank 8: Using Antonym or Contrast Clue in unlocking the meaning of unfamiliar words; Rank 9: Determining the meaning of words and expressions through Definition or Statement Clue; and Rank 10: Determining the meaning of words and expressions through Synonym or Restatement Clue.

Evaluation of the Expert-Respondents and the Teacher-Respondents on the Developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners

Table 2. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners as Regards Content Quality

Indicators	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	4.00	SA	3.87	SA
2. Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	3.87	SA	3.80	SA
3. Content is accurate.	3.87	SA	3.67	SA
4. Content is up-to-date.	3.73	SA	3.73	SA
5. Content is logically developed and organized.	3.87	SA	3.60	SA
6. Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	3.73	SA	3.80	SA
7. Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	3.93	SA	3.73	SA
8. Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3.80	SA	3.73	SA
9. Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	4.00	SA	3.87	SA
10. Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	3.93	SA	3.93	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.87	SA	3.77	SA
Standard Deviation	0.14		0.26	

The results showed overall weighted mean ratings of 3.87 and 3.77, respectively, which were verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree (SA). Meanwhile, the evaluations of the teachers gained a standard deviation of 0.14, while the experts' gained 0.26. It indicates that the content quality of the Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners is aligned with the learning competencies prescribed by the DepEd, ensuring consistency with topics and skills.

This supports the study of Chavez (2019), which claimed that the information will be a helpful resource for the students and that the topics are given in a relatable way. It should contain new and relevant content that will provide students with up-to-date information related to the competencies they need to master.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners as Regards Instructional Quality

Indicators	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Purpose of the material is well defined.	3.93	SA	3.80	SA
2. Material achieves its defined purpose.	3.87	SA	3.67	SA
3. Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	4.00	SA	3.80	SA
4. Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	3.80	SA	3.73	SA
5. Graphics / colors / sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	3.73	SA	3.87	SA
6. Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	3.93	SA	3.87	SA
7. Material effectively stimulates creativity of target user.	3.87	SA	3.87	SA
8. Feedback on target user's responses is effectively employed.	3.87	SA	3.80	SA
9. Target user can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	3.87	SA	3.47	A
10. Instruction is integrated with target user's previous experience.	3.73	SA	3.73	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.86	SA	3.76	SA
Standard Deviation	0.20		0.29	

The table exhibits that both teachers and experts evaluated the developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities in terms of content quality with the overall weighted mean ratings of 3.86 and 3.76, respectively, verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree (SA). It suggests that instructional quality of the developed learning material includes a well-defined purpose, clear and measurable learning goals, appropriate difficulty levels tailored for the target audience, has judicious use of graphics/colors/sounds for instructional purposes, with an enjoyable and stimulating presentation, and adept utilization of feedback on user responses.

The results are in line with the study of Cosmod (2021) which was praised for being extremely beneficial, topical, participatory, understandable, relatable, and with well-defined instructions that are easy to follow by the intended audience.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners as Regards Technical Quality

Indicators	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Audio enhances understanding of the concept.	3.60	SA	3.60	SA
2. Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) is clear and can be easily understood.	3.73	SA	3.13	A
3. There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals.	3.67	SA	3.20	A
4. Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	3.67	SA	3.60	SA
5. Screen displays (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	3.60	SA	3.53	SA
6. Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret.	3.80	SA	3.80	SA
7. Visuals sustain interest and do not distract user's attention.	3.60	SA	3.67	SA
8. Visuals provide accurate representation of the concept discussed.	3.80	SA	3.80	SA
9. The user support materials are effective.	3.87	SA	3.73	SA
10. The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material.	3.73	SA	3.53	SA
11. The material can easily and independently be used.	3.73	SA	3.40	A
12. The material will run using minimum system requirements.	3.53	SA	3.60	SA
13. The program is free from technical problems.	3.47	A	3.20	A
Overall Weighted Mean	3.68	SA	3.52	SA
Standard Deviation	0.32		0.25	

The table displays that both teachers and experts evaluated the developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners in terms of technical quality with the overall weighted mean ratings of 3.68 and 3.52, respectively, verbally interpreted as Strongly Agree (SA). It reveals that the technical quality of the Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners supports the enhancement of concept understanding through the engaging support materials.

This is congruent to the study of Montawar (2023) in which the researchers found that the Digital Supplementary Learning Material are highly relevant and helpful in the modern learning style of the learners.

Test of Significant Difference Between the Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners

Table 5. Test of Significant Difference in the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners as to Content Quality

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	15	3.87	0.14	1.31	2.05	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	15	3.77	0.26				

As a consequence, the null hypothesis is retained at a 5% level of significance. This means that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners in terms of Content Quality.

This implies that the two groups of respondents agreed that the content of the developed enhancement activities is in harmony with DepEd Learning Competencies, facilitating enrichment, reinforcement, and mastery of learning objectives.

Table 6. Test of Significant Difference in the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners as to Instructional Quality

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	15	3.86	0.20	1.10	2.05	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	15	3.76	0.29				

At a 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. This affirms the idea that there is no significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners in terms of Instructional Quality.

This implies that the two groups of respondents believed that the quality of instructions of the developed enhancement activities is highly acceptable as evident by its well-defined purpose, successful achievement of objectives, clear and measurable learning goals, suitable difficulty level, purposeful use of graphics/colors/sounds, enjoyable and engaging content.

Table 7. *Test of Significant Difference in the Respondents' Evaluation on the Developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners as to Technical Quality*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	15	3.68	0.32	1.46	2.05	Fail to reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	15	3.52	0.25				

This leads that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected at a 5% significance level. Hence, there is no significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners in terms of Technical Quality.

This suggests that the two groups of respondents agreed that the developed enhancement activities' technical quality includes audio that facilitates comprehension through clear speech and narration, audio and visuals that are well-synchronized, appropriate music and sound effects, clean and readable screen text, visually engaging presentations, accurate conceptual representation through visuals, a user-friendly design that allows for free navigation, and overall ease of independent use of the material.

Comments/Suggestions Given by the Respondents Relative to the Improvement of the Developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners

The Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities designed for Grade 8 Learners are intended to support students in enhancing both their vocabulary and understanding of the English language.

Taking into consideration, the feedback will enhance the developed material's effectiveness, comprehensiveness, and interactivity while also catering to the interests of the learner, ensuring that they thoroughly enjoy the process of learning new words and skills. The activities surrounding the instructional environment will continue to take shape as the technical and instructional quality of the material improves. Additionally, it will give teachers the ability to focus on specific tasks that will help students apply concepts in real-world settings, which will result in more immersive and group learning possibilities.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

Based on the results of the Phil-IRI, there were least mastered competencies particularly in vocabulary skill which can be addressed through development of vocabulary enhancement activities.

The developed Contextualized e-Game-Based Vocabulary Enhancement Activities for Grade 8 Learners is highly acceptable in terms of the content, instruction, and technical quality of the enhancement activities.

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